

DIHNET final event: Guidelines for chairs, presenters, panellists, and participants.

House Rules for the event

- Please use your name and surname for the identification (to help us find you if needed). Adjust your identification and do not use nicknames, symbols, or strange characters.
- If you are experiencing technical problems, direct your questions to the technical facilitator.
- Questions for individual presentations can be placed in the chat box from the beginning until the end of the presentation; some or all these questions will be taken up by the chair.
- Questions for the Q&A session can be placed into the chat box after the end of the last presentation.
- For both types of questions, we kindly ask participants to introduce themselves and to keep their questions short and concise.
- This event will be recorded and published in DIHNET communication channels.
- Tweeting: use the hashtags #DIHNETfinalevent and @DihnetE

Information for Chairs

- Each session will be chaired by a designated DIHNET colleague, who will open the session.
- The chairs enter the WebEx meeting room preferably 30 minutes and at least 15 minutes before the start of the session. They need to make sure all presenters and panellists are in the meeting. If this is not the case, the chairs inform the technical facilitator.
- The chair opens and closes the session, and makes sure that all participants adhere to the “House Rules” of sessions. The chairs introduce presenters and panellists, keep the time, select questions from the chat box with the support of the technical facilitator, and lead the discussion.
 - Time keeping: The chairs will signal 5/1/0 min left to presenters. If a presenter is not finished after 5 minutes, the chairs will have to cut short the presentation, by kindly asking the presenter to conclude and by muting the presenter after 10 minutes (from the time limit). If the chair does not follow the time keeping process, the technical facilitator will intervene making herself visible on the screen and kindly ask the chair to keep the time.
 - Q&A: If presenters or panellists do not receive any question from the audience, the chairs might step in and ask questions.
- At the end of each session, the chair will thank all presenters, panellists, and participants for their contributions.
- In order to maintain orderly discussions, the chairs, together with the technical facilitator, may turn off video, mute and exclude participants from the session at his/her discretion.

Information for Presenters

- Before the event, the chair will provide you with the format of the session (including times), as it varies among sessions. Please follow those indications.
- The presentation should be in PowerPoint or a PDF.
- Please make sure that you stick to the time and keep your slides to a minimum and do not overload your slides with too much text and information.
- Please make your presentation accessible to a diverse audience (i.e., people from DIHs, RTOs, DIH networks, policy makers, member states, researchers, companies, investors, etc.)
- You may prepare or use an existing background image of your institution to be used in WebEx.
- Please enter the virtual meeting room well before the start of the session, preferably 30 min and at least 15 minutes before the start of the session in which you present.

Information for Panellists

- Before the event, the chair will provide you with the format of the session (including times), as it varies among sessions. Please follow those indications.
- Please enter the virtual meeting room well before the start of the session, preferably 30 minutes and at least 15 minutes before the start of the session in which you will serve as panellist.
- You may prepare or use an existing background image of your institution to be used in WebEx.

Information for Participants

- Participants are automatically muted at the beginning of the event.
- During the presentations, participants may write clarification questions to the presenters in the chat box. Some or all these questions will be taken up by the chairs.
- During the Q&A session, participants may place their questions in the chat box or may raise their hands to share their insights or ask a question, upon invitation by the chair.
- Please formulate your comments in a respectful and constructive way.
- Tweeting: use the hashtags #DIHNETfinalevent and @DihnetE

